

EDUCATION OF YOUNG BOYS AGAINST GENDER VIOLENCE IN ALBANIA		Education Keywords: gender violence, domestic violence, bullying, sexual harassment, peer education programs.
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Ela Tollkuçi	PhD (candidate) student Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies, Tirana, Albania
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Abstract

The prevention of gender violence among young boys at the primary and secondary schools in Albania is considered important during the projects implementation of NGOs dealing with domestic violence. This paper consider the perspective according to which, sustainable programs for the `Non-violence` education of young boys in the schools, are achieved only if we exalt the historical memory of peaceful citizenship. This ongoing educational goal should include also campaigns for arising awareness, treatments of youths exposed to violence and abuse in the families and also it is needed to involve young people from communities where criminal activities, bullying and sexual harassment in schools are present. According to recent studies, these factors warn on future domestic violence risks. Albania lacks of programs that in European Union countries constitute the standardized and accredited informative activities for young people. Workshops that raise awareness on vulnerability must be placed together with preventive programs for peer education.

Introduction

The contemporary philosophical thought on violence is reconsidered in the analysis of Aldo Capiti¹. When we think about violence, we are inclined to orient ourselves towards the concept of war in all the varieties in which it emerge. Consequently, stereotypes of atrocities and human suffering, compose everyone's imaginary scenario and present themselves as elements that feed the fear from the concept of war in its complexity. This is the result of lack of food resources, psychological suffering in the collective manifestation of panic, forms of anxiety and depression, trauma from the loss of close relatives and the inability for psychological recover from the loss of limbs in case of war incidents. In reality, violence must be seen beyond extreme situations and must be unfortunately considered in our daily lives. We refer here, not only to gender, racial and ethnic violence, or even to community, school and family one, but to a more latent dimension that requires the ability and attention of a researcher to analyze it. This is what we refer to as "violence form the system". The economic, financial and social system, seen from the perspective of both a single state and also in relations between states, has led to such a degree of social inequality to fuel feelings of hatred, caused by frustration, towards the poorest groups of the young. The feeling is that of an equivalent experience of humiliation, physical and emotional violence by individuals with better economic opportunities. If we refer to concrete examples, experience provides us with cases of everyday life that derive from regional situations to those of inequality at world level. So, if we consider for example a teenager, born and raised in the deepest villages of Albania with lack of social support, we can imagine how the lack of a crossing bridge, breaks also the bond and the possibility to communicate between worlds and different realities.

¹ M. Catarci (2013), Il pensiero disarmato: La pedagogia della nonviolenza di Aldo Capitini. EGA, Torino, Italy, p 17-22.

What can we say to a young boy raised in the suburbs or to a beggar who lives in extreme poverty, when they visit the neighborhoods of the capital among perfumes, gold, brands, fantastic restaurants, giant glass buildings and machines that seem to belong to a totally incoherent reality with that of a few miles away? What could we tell to the young boys from 'Favelas' neighborhoods in Rio de Janeiro while strolling across the long sea of Copagabana and Ipanema in all their magical splendor? How can we combine the profound inequalities of South Africa to a rational discourse that calms from emotional intensity? How can we explain today to a young boy with the due tranquility and necessary argumentation that two percent of the world population has more than half of the wealth and that the remaining poorer part must survive with less than one percent of the wealth of all world population². The well-being concept of positivist psychology would be threatened by the lack of social and economic elements of this holistic system³. Such reality unfortunately becomes potential for the growth of young people deprived from all that their senses perceive and send from everyday life. The anger felt towards all those who possess goods will be transformed into a strong compensatory mechanism which will then come to constitute their own personality.

Main Structure

The global education⁴ of young people, especially at the middle school level, has become a necessity and is based on the operation of long-term programs in education against violence. Unfortunately, human culture strongly relies on violence and therefore the task of educating remain in the pedagogical practice. The school has the potential to complete its peaceful function through profound restructuring of the dominant minds. It is about balancing the collective imagination, the ideals of heroes who bring justice with the use of weapons and bloody heroes, using the peaceful narratives that must be performed as a break from the endless hostilities. People are so unused to ``non-violence`` that even the use of a descriptive term suitable for it becomes difficult to find in our lexicon. We are used to such adaptations: non-violence, against violence, peacefully, but never an appropriate term to show the true "non-violent" act. The educational process, in all its scope that goes beyond school premises, including media and multimedia, literary and artistic books, theaters and cinemas, should become the mediator for delegitimizing violence in all scenarios of cultural and social heritage. The demand for this mission will be based again on the sources of tradition in which each culture has the strength and peaceful potential to bring changes. It is only in the general context of this point of view that a new society could be formed without the tragic and triumphant memory of violence. Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) is considered a phenomenon with devastating effects on women, children and men⁵.

² W. Naudé., (2009), «The financial crisis of 2008 and developing countries». Discussion paper no. 2009/01, United Nations University, UNU-WIDER, Helsinki, p 6-7.

³ A. Delle Fave., 2007. La condivisione del benessere. Il contributo della psicologia positive. FrancoAngeli s.r.l., Milano, Italy, p 113-129.

⁴ M. Catarci (2013), Il pensiero disarmato: La pedagogia della nonviolenza di Aldo Capitini. EGA, Torino, Italy, p 51-67.

⁵ L. S. Kimberg., (2008). Addressing Intimate Partner Violence with Male Patients: A Review and Introduction of Pilot Guidelines. Journal of General Internal Medicine, vol. 23, 12, p 2071-2078.

This phenomenon is not always seen as associated with all parts of the society. It is considered a widespread social problem throughout the world that affects and damages the well-being of women in different age groups. F. G. Kouyoumdjian⁶ considers it a behavior within an intimate relationship that causes physical, sexual or psychological damage, including acts of physical aggression, sexual intercourse, psychological abuse and control behavior. This is a definition that today is associated with the concept of IPV, whose origin, according to the intercultural studies of the World Health Organization⁷, derived from violence within the family.

According to the World Health Organization⁸, the worldwide rate of violence against women varies from 15% to 71%. If we refer to percentages of past violence experiences, these figures range from 4% to 54%. The values are expected to be even higher if we refer to the estimates of psychological violence and behavioral control. In this context, IPV is not only a worldwide phenomenon, but also has considerable consequences with physical and psychological damage to the victim, which makes it a serious health problem⁹. According to the Swedish National Health and Wellbeing Council in 2006¹⁰, the annual expenses relating to domestic violence, which in Sweden amount to 3.3 billion SEK, is of 38 million only in medical expenses.

According to recent data reported in Sweden, there is a significant increase in complaints to the police by the younger population, linked to cases of rape and workplace violence, in particular compared to thirty and forty years ago. Even hospital statistics in Sweden show an increase in the number of assistance required following sexual violence. Another problem that has emerged from the surveys and research is the mistreatment of women during the period of pregnancy. Gianotti in 2007¹¹ records the data reported by the Journal of Family Violence (2004) and the Pan American Health Organization (2005), according to which this delicate phenomenon in America has serious implications not only for the mothers but also for physical traumas to newborns. Violence against women during pregnancy is associated with a high probability of chronic trauma associated with a symptom of post-traumatic stress disorder. In a cyclical form this situation of the mother exacerbates her ability to take care of the child, thus compromising health, normal development and relationship with the mother. The presence of the child during repeated episodes of violence against one of the parents has been shown to be associated with psychological disorders, drugs and alcohol dependences, criminal behavior and suicide attempts¹².

⁶ F. G. Kouyoumdjian, L. M.a. Calzavara, S. J.a. Bondy, P. O'Campo, D. Serwadda, F. Nalugoda, J. Kagaayi, G. Kigozi, M. Wawer, R. Gray, Rond., (2013). Intimate partner violence is associated with incident HIV infection in women in Uganda. *AIDS*, Volume 27, 8, p 1331–1338

⁷ World Health Organization., (2008). *World health statistics 2008*, WHO Press, Geneva, Switzerland, p 10-12

⁸ *Ibidem*, p 10-12.

⁹ J. Ntaganira, A. S. Muula, F. Masaisa, F. Dusabeyezu, S. Siziya, E. Rudatsikira., (2008) E. Intimate partner violence among pregnant women in Rwanda. *BMC Womens Health*, 8, p 17.

¹⁰ K. Leander, M. Berlin, A. Eriksson, K. Gillander, G. Hensing, G. Krantz, K. Swahnberg, M. Danielsson., (2012). Violence. Health in Sweden: The National Public Health Report 2012. Chapter 12. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*, 40, 9, p 229–254.

¹¹ M. A. Gainotti., (2007). La violenza domestica. Comunicazione presentata alla Giornata di Studio "I Centri Antiviolenza a Roma e in Italia: prassi e ricerca". Facoltà di Scienze della Formazione – Università di Roma Tre, p 15-16

¹² *Ibidem*, p 16-19.

Among the mental health disorders that involve women victims of violence we could mention suicidal ideas, comorbidity of post-traumatic stress disorders and suicidal ideas, gynecological and obstetric disorders associated with chronic abdominal pain and premature births¹³. Another important aspect is the strong link between relations with a violent partner and the likelihood to encounter sexual transmitted infections STD and the human immunodeficiency virus known as HIV. In a study in which the risk of sexual transmitted diseases and HIV were estimated¹⁴, the link between these diseases and violent sexual intercourse reached 51.6% in adolescents diagnosed with following pathologies. Studies¹⁵ stresses the fact that the probability of encountering HIV infection in married women in India, who suffer physical and sexual violence from their spouses, is four times higher than women who have no experience of violence from the partner. This risk is duplicated by the fact that is accompanied by both high predisposition of these violent male for high-risk behaviors, which in turn increase the likelihood of infection with STD and HIV (unprotected relationships with many partners)¹⁶ and also because women themselves have low levels of control over sexual relations with these partners. The risk index for HIV infection is consequently not influenced by sexual behavior at high risk of sexual transmission of the women (unprotected sex behaviors and with many partners). The percentage of Indian women who have more than one sexual partner is very low. This fact is the consequence of gender differences that in India mostly influences sexual dimension.

These evidences from the Indian context are overturned in the case of African women, where, according to the data, 44% of women who attend prenatal counselling turn out to have been in several sexual relations over the time. For these reasons, in the case of Indian women, their infection from HIV is correlated with the degree of non protected sexual relations that their spouses have had with other women and that at the same time have had also violent sexual relations with them. Another indirect problem of domestic violence are the implications in the new generations. Child-assisted violence, which in itself is a form of maltreatment against them, has not only long-term consequences, but is also seen as an element that is transmitted from one generation to another¹⁷. This transmissive aspect of violence transcends the boundaries of the family context and appears in forms of violence against schoolmates, friends and also teachers.

Baldry in 2003¹⁸ underlines the fact that children exposed to domestic violence not only show bullying behavior to their schoolmates, but are also victims of this behavior by others. This latter data appears in 71% of cases in children affected by assisted violence and are associated with low levels of self-esteem, fear and depression that accompany them in the family context.

¹³ J. Ntaganira, A. S. Muula, F. Masaisa, F. Dusabeyezu, S. Siziya, E. Rudatsikira., (2008) E. Intimate partner violence among pregnant women in Rwanda. *BMC Womens Health*, 8, p 17.

¹⁴ J. G. Silverman, M. R. Decker, N. A. Kapur, J. Gupta, A. Raj., (2007). Violence against wives, sexual risk and sexually transmitted infection among Bangladeshi men. *Sexually Transmitted Infections*, vol 83, 3, p 211-215.

¹⁵ J. G. Silverman, M. R. Decker, N. Saggurti, D. Balaiah, A. Raj., (2008). Intimate Partner Violence and HIV Infection Among Married Indian Women. *JAMA*, vol. 300, 6, p 703-710

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, p 703-710.

¹⁷ M. A. Gainotti., (2007). La violenza domenicca. Comunicazione presentata alla Giornata di Studio“ I Centri Antiviolenza a Roma e in Italia: prassi e ricerca”. Facoltà di Scienze della Formazione – Università di Roma Tre, p 16-19.

¹⁸ A. C. Baldry., 2003. Bullying in schools and exposure to domestic violence. *Child Abuse Negl.* 27, (7), p 713-732.

According to Naqi and Tremblay in 2001¹⁹, there is a highly predictive link between high levels of hyperactivity and childhood obesity in kindergartens in proportion to the increasing of aggression. This result and the identification of a significant link between aggression and the premature maternity in adolescents with low level of education, are two significant results in the study with boys of the age 6 to 15 years old from a Canadian sample. The results of the above studies, are supplemented with those on bullying faced by children and young people in schools, linked to low levels of social adaptation, and have great potential to be predictors of violence during adulthood²⁰.

These experiences include not only assisted violence, but also experiences of violence and sexual abuse during childhood, exposure to violent communities and participation in juvenile delinquency groups. Bullying in schools is defined as a repeated physical or psychological aggression against another student, which is perceived by the aggressor as weaker and less powerful²¹. Men who reported bully behavior at school during childhood are more likely to become partners with physical and sexual assault behaviors²². This result is seen as proof of the direct link between child bullying and the predisposition to have future intimate violent partner. It is reported that bullying behavior is more prevalent in males than in women and more in middle school than in high school students. The phenomenon of bullying is a very serious problem in the United States and appears in different forms in men and women. Forms of physical and verbal bullying are more common in men, while provocations, negative sexual comments and rumors about the targeted person predominate in females. There is awareness in Albania on the phenomenon of bullying that is reflected in the activation of the bodies responsible for the development of educational programs, reports of various organizations with respect to the protection of children's rights and an academic and research work aimed at analyzing the situation in country. However, the initiatives undertaken by these institutions remain few with respect to the objective of reducing this phenomenon in the schools.

Among the main problems that the few studies conducted in Albania identify as important regarding this phenomenon we can mention: the lack of adequate information of school teachers which leave to indifference or occasional attitudes any act regarding this phenomenon^{23,24}; a connection of this phenomenon to the social and economic situation and origins of the family; prejudices and sexual preferences about the young victim of bullying^{25,26}.

¹⁹ D. S. Nagin, R. E. Tremblay., 2001. Parental and Early Childhood Predictors of Persistent Physical Aggression in Boys from Kindergarten to High School. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, vol. 58, 4, p 389-394.

²⁰ K. L. Falb, L. McCauley, M. R. Decker, J. Gupta, A. Raj, J. G. Silverman., (2011). School Bullying Perpetration and Other Childhood Risk Factors as Predictors of Adult Intimate Partner Violence Perpetration. *Archives Pediatrics Adolescent Medicine*, vol. 165, 10, p 890-894.

²¹ A. C. Baldry., 2003. Bullying in schools and exposure to domestic violence. *Child Abuse Negl.* 27, (7), p 713-732.

²² K. L. Falb, L. McCauley, M. R. Decker, J. Gupta, A. Raj, J. G. Silverman., (2011). School Bullying Perpetration and Other Childhood Risk Factors as Predictors of Adult Intimate Partner Violence Perpetration. *Archives Pediatrics Adolescent Medicine*, vol. 165, 10, p 890-894.

²³ F. Hasekiu., 1997. Bullying: Incidence, Impact, and Intervention. Faculty of Education Sciences, Department of Psychology, "Aleksander Xhuvani" University, Elbasan, Albania, p 21-27.

²⁴ L. Kashahu, Th. Karaj., 2014. Perceptimet dhe Qëndrimet e Mësuesve dhe Drejtuesve të Shkollave 9-Vjeçare mbi Fenomenin e Bullizmit. *BJES*, vol. 6, 1, p 35-48.

²⁵ Ibidem, p 35-48.

²⁶ ALO., 2013. Raport Analitik i ALO 116, p 4-9. www.alo116.al/sites/default/files/uploade/Bulizmi.pdf

The prevention of this phenomenon in our context is seen in relation to awareness-raising activities for students, manuals for the identification and treatment of bullying by teachers and the enrichment of curricula with educational and social subjects of different level of knowledge in this regard²⁷. Beyond the good willing to raise awareness and educate young people of middle and high schools on issues related to violence in Albania, there is still a huge amount of work to be done especially for the empowerment and involvement of young people as the main promoters against violence on their peers. So far, good work has been done to promote and raise awareness among young people about domestic violence, school and gender violence. In this context, the role of NGOs has been crucial by becoming the prime catalysts that together with the ministries, school directories and educational institutions themselves, have provided information and raised awareness to students about the phenomenon of violence during the course of this years. Bearing in mind all the positive and negative aspects that have characterized the implementation of this process, as well as the challenges that undeniably still need to be overcome, we can say that in general we are at a good point regarding informing youths on the general concept of violence, violence against youths in families and schools, on gender and ethnic violence and less on homophobic violence. A large part of youths throughout the Albanian territory are informed about the characteristics of all these forms of violence and recognize the state and private institutions to which they can turn to report and obtain protection. There is still another new objective for the Albanian reality and that is strengthening of youths as the most important promoters against this phenomenon among peers not only in the school context, but also in the family, community and society as a whole. This challenge requires a multifactorial intervention that involves the improvement of the school curriculum, the training of school directors, teachers and psychologists and the integration of long-term programs for the empowerment of young people against violence. In this regard, the experience of United States of America provides us with studies, some of which are follow-up, which refer to intervention programs in preschool and school age^{28,29}. Albania also has several years of awareness-raising initiatives and prevention on gender violence among young people in middle and high schools. Such an initiative is the promotion and appropriation of the New Methods of Discipline (NMD) in the context of the implementation of the Commitment to Change Behavior program³⁰, which reproduces the idea of a complex and continuous education against violence. The institution of "non-violence" begins by generating an educational system that promotes friendly, positive and peaceful attitudes and behaviors of teachers in programs that orient towards citizenship of youths in family, community and cultural contexts that distance themselves from violence and its projections. In this four-year lifelong learning program, the new educational form is implemented through four communication aspects (Stop, Ask, Include and Undertake) represented by the acronym SAIU.

²⁷ L. Kashahu, Th. Karaj., 2014. Perceptimet dhe Qëndrimet e Mësuesve dhe Drejtuesve të Shkollave 9-Vjeçare mbi Fenomenin e Bullizimit. BJES, vol. 6, 1, p 35-48.

²⁸ A. J. Reynolds, J. A. Temple, S. Ou, D. L. Robertson, J. P. Mersky, J. W. Topitzes, M. D. Niles., 2007. Effects of a School-Based, Early Childhood Intervention on Adult Health and Well-being. Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med, vol. 161, 8, p 730-739.

²⁹ J. A. Mytton, C. DiGuseppi, D. A. Gough, R. S. Taylor, S. Logan., 2002. School-Based Violence Prevention Programs. Systematic Review of Secondary Prevention Trials. Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med, vol. 156, 8, p 752-762.

³⁰ D. Grillo, F. Hima., 2012. Parandalimi i Dhunës si Mënyrë Edukimi në Shkolla. Konferenca Shkencore: Dhuna kundër Fëmijëve në Shqipëri. Si e parandalojnë dhunën kundër fëmijëve sistemi i mbrojtjes sociale dhe shërbimet sociale në Shqipëri? PEGI, Lundër, Tiranë, Albania, p 96-102.

The education of the students starts first of all by educating teachers in the process of communication that inhibits and controls violent behavior. Before any impulsive action, questioning and negotiating with the cases constitute the prerequisites for a less derogatory, aggressive and violent behavior. Despite the example of a successful initiative, much remains to be done, in particular with regard to the aspects linked to the violence of youths among them and specifically those based on gender. The effective work carried out so far in this regard is linked to the awareness-raising activity of NGOs with middle and high school students in the Albanian territory. These activities consist mainly in workshops with a duration of several hours for the realization of which there is no obligation to follow high impact manuals and standard strategies.

Mostly, the trainer respects the obligations to inform about the different types of gender violence, its psycho and physical consequences, the institutional role for the help to the victims of violence as well as the legislative changes and measures that have been taken for banning the aggressors. We rely on the ability, being informed and the experience of the trainer for the willing to realize the complexity of the problem so that the activity has a long term impact on youths. An example of workshop against gender violence with young boys is the one carried out with middle school students in the Municipality of Domë in Tirana³¹. It was planned to familiarize the students with the concept of empathy towards the other, with the different forms of physical, psychological and economic violence, to enhance their knowledge for the long-term physical and psychological consequences of exposure to the violence, familiarize with the institutions dealing with the protection, prevention and integration of victims of violence, with the legislation in favor of the victims of violence and with the concept of "Love", based on Sternberg's model of complete love triangle³² as an important and comprehensive dimension of human life that guarantees the control of aggressive behavior towards intimate partner. All these phases were accompanied by illustrations of concrete cases, discussions, the technique of incomplete sentence, listing and illustrating items, role-plays and symbols for the development of creative activities (field games, e.g. soccer).

Sustainable improvements would be made for the development of activities against gender violence, once educational organizations and institutions will be based on real programs developed within the framework of cooperation between organizations present in different countries. One of such programs is the Promotion of Awareness for the Prevention of Gender Violence through Peer Education³³³⁴. This program include a considerable prolonged period of training, sections during which complementary activities are developed in well-defined periods, training for youths as future experts on the issue of gender violence in peer groups, profound and detailed knowledge of all the aspects of gender violence among youths and their empowerment by becoming the main

³¹ The workshop is part of a project of the center for counseling of women and girls (2014) at is organized twice a year during which activities are planned for students of middle and high schools on the theme of prevention of gender violence. These initiatives are linked to the high predisposition of young boys in this age to identify with the role of the aggressor in their relations to the other gender.

³² Sternberg's model of the triangle of complete love includes elements of passion, intimacy, and commitment.

³³ A. Pana, S. Lesta., 2012. Youth4Youth. Promuovere la sensibilizzazione nella Prevenzione della Violenza di Genere tramite l'Educazione tra Pari. Istituto Mediterraneo sugli Studi di Genere, Nicosia, Cyprus, p 10-15.

³⁴ Partner organizations that have participated in the drafting of this project are: European Anti-Violence Network (EAVN), Grecia; Casa delle Donne per non Subire Violenza, Italia; Women's Issues Information Centre (WIIC), Lituania; Centre of Research in Theories and Practices that Overcome Inequalities (CREA), Università di Barcellona, Spagna.

agents of peer change and for the community as a whole, the use of exercises related to the assessment of attitudes and behaviors, discussions, the exercise of "living in a box", scenarios of gender violence, role-playing games, brainstorming and laboratory activities such as film presentations, photographic exhibitions and posters, preparation of themes and articles, theatrical performances, interviews with trained students on the radio and on central and local TV.

Conclusion

The education of youths in schools, in the recent years, is increasingly seen as a process that implies new educational orientations. We must consider education as a more spiritual approach. The lyrical cultural heritage rather than the epic one, spiritual heroes rather than bloody ones, diplomatic policies rather than fighting ones, must reach a balance and timely orient themselves towards more peaceful experiences and forms. Schools should emphasize spiritual victory and the victory of "non-violence" by giving the necessary space to the new man of the future. The models of heroes against violence, should the same come from the historical past and the cultural heritage of the nation, but should be read with a new spirit and in a more peaceful context that takes the cue from the philosophy of Gandhi, Martin Luther King and Nelson Mandela. As Aldo Capitini says³⁵: *“Historians need to recognize that from a historical point of view it is not correct that peaceful people always lose while the violent win... Spartacus and his people have achieved nothing; while Gandhi won without touching even a hair to the British soldiers and their families in India and William Pen presented himself with his friends ‘Quakers’ to the pink skins, without weapons, making sure that their leaders threw away their weapons, thus creating a state of peace that differed from all other North American nations. There are also victories without violence”*. Of course, the journey towards such a future is still long and takes time to educate youths to the awareness of the non-violence. The process is slow, but when it will occur, with great probability, it will be persistent and permanent. As long as such a school curricula will take place, it would be necessary to continue with a strong work of awareness and responsibility against every violent act expressed in any type of context. More specifically, in relation to the education against gender violence for middle and high school youths, world experience considers long-term training programs as highly effective. One of these programs is "youth to youth" for the promotion of awareness on the prevention of gender violence through education among young people³⁶. Its most interesting feature is the division into six sections, each of which has a specific training objective. In the first section, students get familiar with the concept of gender roles and the expectations that are based on these roles by the family, the community and the tools of mass communication. They also learn to critically view gender roles as well as the problems of inequality they bring. The second section deals with the issue of gender violence in the school context.

³⁵ Psicologia della nonviolenza. A cura di Filippo Trasatti, p 12-14.
http://www.ficemea.org/IMG/Pedagogie_de_la_nonviolence_40TEMA.pdf

³⁶A. Pana, S. Lesta., 2012. Youth4Youth. Promuovere la sensibilizzazione nella Prevenzione dellaViolenza di Genere tramite l’Educazione tra Pari. Istituto Mediterraneo sugli Studi diGenere, Nicosia, Cyprus, p 10-15.

This information is provided through the transition from a broader concept of gender violence to gender bullying in schools. The third section deals with the concept of gender violence in intimate relationships. The goal is to teach students to avoid romantic perceptions of violence related primarily to its psychological elements. In the fourth section, it takes place the training for becoming an educator among peers. The purpose is to acquire all the skills to become future operators who will work in school premises. The sixth section concerns the application of trained students as peer educators. What's important in this phase is the free decision-making process of the coach-student on the activities and the number of sections that he/she will conduct with the peers. The last section, which is also the most entertaining one, consist on artistic and follow-up activities during which the students prepare artistic parts, films and exhibitions of different character in the function of a complete communication with their peers. This program lasts for few months and has a "snowball" effect on the young people who are involved. His model is based on the new teaching mentality according to which training and practice are the most effective for the complete acquisition of the knowledge. This is the reason why it is used to say "Experience is the mother of knowledge".

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